

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B103
Date: 16 Jun 2005
Take Off: 10:50:02
Landing: 14:14:52
Flight Time: 3h24m50

Campaign: CLOPAP
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: N Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics Training	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / WAS	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
9	CVI	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
10	CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
11	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
12	AMS	Johnny Crosier	Manchester University
13	NOxy	Andy MacDonald	UEA
14	ADA / CPI	Michael Flynn	Manchester University
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B103 Track 16-JUN-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B103
 Date: 16/06/05
 Project: CLOPAP
 Location: N Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
093712		Start posn	0.21 kft	126	52'04.36N,0'37.48W
103351		INU	0.00 kft	126	Set to Navigate
105002		T/O	0.00 kft	251	From Cranfield
105933		NOxy	10.0 kft	009	Cals
105950		Videos	10.0 kft	009	Start FFC & DFC
112520	113509	Profile 1	10.0 - 0.02 kft	178	B-A, down to 50'
114428	115742	Run 1	3.0 kft	326	1015mB,clear air,A-B
114834		Video	3.0 kft	326	restart FFC, tape chewed
120313	121749	Run 2	2.0 kft	158	In cloud, B-A
122651	123956	Run 3	1.2 kft	327	A-B
124523	125901	Run 4	3.0 kft	160	B-A,above cloud
131644	132501	Run 5	1.0 - 0.92 kft	339	C-D, below cloud

Abandon mission, wx conditions too messy

134444		NOxy	10.0 kft	208	Cals
140248		ASPs	9.3 kft	196	Closed
141452		Land	0.21 kft	300	At Cranfield
141944		Stop posn	0.19 kft	027	52'04.38N,0'37.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B103 Track 16-JUN-05

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP (Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud) : T.W.Choularton/|KNB

Scientific Aims:

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected to the northeast over East Anglia and the North Sea in cloudy conditions. Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume change, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

Weather conditions

A stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over the sea downwind of a main source of air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

All instruments to be operated continuously.

1) Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations,
- ADA – as above
- CCN* - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- Ice Nucleus counter* (INC) normally operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to a different set of conditions.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- TWC – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

Chemistry Measurements

- 2) WAS - 2 bottle samples per 10min flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist.
- 3) NO_x, Ozone, SO₂, CO, PTRMS, Hydrogen peroxide to operate continuously.
- 4) AMS - to be operated on Rosemount inlet out of cloud, CVI inlet in cloud if possible. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.
- 5) Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear.

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud

Flight Number : B103

Date: 16 June 2005

Mission Scientist: Phil Brown

Sortie Aims: To study the evolution of aerosol in cloud as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol with cloud both as the aerosol modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol.

Sortie Location: Area of low cloud over the western N Sea, looking at the interaction with air advecting westwards from the continent. The cloud region is expected to be present from the east coast of England and out eastwards of the Wash area into the North Sea. The flying should start either at the upwind cloud edge or as far out upwind (eastwards) as possible (up to 200 km).

Sortie Summary: The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of 100 km transects (straight and level runs – SLRs) across the plume within the boundary layer, one below cloud, one in cloud and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects will be immediately preceded by a vertical profile extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible. These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals of about 50km downwind to obtain up to 4 sets of transects. Although we are not aiming to perform a comprehensive Lagrangian study, this flight plan will allow us to approximately track the same air as it is advects downwind of the source region and to examine its evolution as it interacts with the low cloud.

Sortie Detail

- a) Take off and climb to FL 110 for transit at cruise speed to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent carrying out NO_x calibration at that level)
- b) T+ 55 When starting region is reached over N. Sea (upwind E edge of cloud bank or 200km out) descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform profile ascent P1 (at 1000 ft per minute) to pass through cloud layer to an altitude 100 ft above cloud top and the boundary layer top.
- c) T+ 73 Descend (not profile descent) to below cloud base, perform a straight and level run below cloud base (200 ft below cloud base) across wind for about 100 km (or long enough for measurements / calibrations to be made - 12 mins) - mission scientist to announce “out of cloud” transect at start.
- d) T+ 90 Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Perform a straight and level run of length 100 km (or less – say 12 mins) across wind in cloud) (if cloud layer deep enough mission scientist may request 2 in cloud transects one near cloud base one near cloud top) - Mission Scientist to announce “in cloud” transect at start.
- e) T+104 Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top, turn through 180 degrees, and perform straight and level run of length 100 km (or less – say 12 mins) across wind - Mission scientist to announce “out of cloud” transect at start.
- f) T+118 Ascend (if required) and cruise to 50 km downwind of initial stack of SLRs and repeat b to e.
- g) Ascend to transit level to travel a further 50 km downwind and repeat b to e
- h) Continue repetitions until available flight time in science area is exhausted
- i) T+240 Climb to transit level to return to home base (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)
- j) T+280 Land.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

P
HILL
Brown

Flight No **B.103**.....

Date **16/6/05**.....

Page **1** of **4**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1037					engine start.
1050					T/O roll.
		1200			cloud base here.
		2450			and top.
1053		3500 ⁷			Sc top is wavy due to slight orog. effect. Mostly 8/8 but ocean hole in wave trough.
/		5000			another thin cloud layer
/		8500			through another thin layer.
/					RUSH dropout just after T/O so can't plot T ₀ for initial climbout
/					Two Neuz all zeroed.
1109		10000			
1113		"			Approaching end of Norway cal. Multilayered cloud, but lowest looks broken out to E. See various orog. effects in cloud layer below this level.
112520		10000	178		Start Profile A
		6500			Cloud layer.
		6000			Another layer.
		5000			Clear at this level.
/					T almost with normal below 8000ft.
		3700			Cloud layer here.
		2700			
					End Profile

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....103.....
 FAAM © 2004

 Date16/6/05.....

 Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1142		¹⁰¹⁵ 3000			Route for run start at A.
	R1	3000	331		Start R1 A → B
—					Wind. 218 / 18 ms ⁻¹
—					Go thro some cloud layers
—					Cloud is more broken to E but also to W towards land.
1149		"			Flamboro Hld ahead.
115319		"			Into cloud briefly - layers get close together.
115742		"			End R1 B desc. to 2000
115920		"			Rain here.
120313		2000			Start R2. ^{should be} B → A below the lowest cloud layer
—		"			
		"			Approaching end of run
		"			Now above the lowest layer again. Aim 1200 ft for next level.
1630 1218 ish		"			End R2 descend in turn.
—					Horace fine probes from halfway along R3
		1200			Seems a good subcloud level
122651		1200	328	⁵³⁰⁷ 0.2E	Start R3 A → B
—					Seems ~ 2-300 ft below base as reqd for subcloud.
					Wind 200° / 13.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**..... 103
 FAAM © 2004

Date 6/6/05

Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123700					puller phone
123956		2000		56.4 0.3W	End R3 bit of rain at end.
					Climb to 3000 looking for above cloud
		3000			looking for another above cloud
/					leg. Briefly in cloud as tops are variable due to wave activity
124523		3000		56.4 0.2W	Start R4 2 photos of wavy cloud top on this run
/					Still some cloud penetrations
/					along run due to wavy top.
125901		11			End R4 Climb to
/					4500 & move to CD line.
1312		4500			In cloud for a time. will profile descent to 1000.
		3000			
131644		1000	327		R5 C→D.
/					Precip cells ahead.
132501		11			End 5 & end of science
/					Cloud layer not made it this far
/					
1333		4000 ↗			Can see there was a wisp of cloud layer between 1000 & 4000 but not well defined. Still basically in isothermal layer of frontal zone.
					on transit, lowest cloud layer is still quite broken in patches
1345		10000			over the coast (thunder est).

2h

2h30

2h

FLIGHT NUMBER: B103	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP	
PROJECT: CLOPAP			

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT			
POST FLIGHT			

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)							
NO (ppbV)							
NO₂ (ppbV)							
NO_x (ppbV)							
SO₂ (ppbV)							

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS
<p>TDLAS switched on @ 0940 Problem with co lamp on pre flight – eventually lit – no explanation CCM training so no zeros</p>

FLIGHT NUMBER: B103	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP	
PROJECT: CLOPAP			

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	14/6/05	77.35	87.42	6761.94

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
110000	100	74.15	88.28	6545.69	50		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
111411	100	55	BAD CAL	REDONE			
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
11:15:00	100	74.27	88.79	6594.87	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.78	0.7	0.7	1.086	0.065	0.351
Time	Flight Level	CO					
Cal performed	Moved to WAS	No detail					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:26:23		77.76	85.65	6737.68	50		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER: B103	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP	
PROJECT: CLOPAP			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B103

Date: 16 Jun 2005

Operator: PAPJ/JC

Page 1 of 2

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:50											Take off, Cranfield Heaters on
11:25:20	60	0.07	151	10							Start P1
11:27:00	28	0.4	165	1000	100	150	12				FI70
11:30:30	1.7	0.1	179	2000							FI40
11:33:00	373	0.09	197	20							FI20
11:34:00	471	0.09	197	10							FI10 End p1
11:44:30	9.25	0.09	199	<10							Run 1
11:46:30	18	0.09	199	<10							
11:48:30	18	0.09	205	<10							
11:50:30	32	0.1	205	<10							
11:54:30	45	0.1	218	1000	26	200	12				
11:57:30	45	0.46	311	2000	36	350	1	3000			End run 1
12:03:30	203	0.1	993	100	30	350	1	6000	500		Run 2
12:06:30	400	0.23	1017	800	29	600	1	7000			
12:08:30	290	0.2	1072	3000							
12:11:00	94	0.1	1121		10	300	1	1000			
12:13:00	165	0.1	1124	<10							
12:18:00											End run 2
122651	250	0.09	1141	70							Start run 3 @ 1200ft
1228	230	0.09	1141	80							
1230	260	0.09	1141	80							
1232	370	0.09	1141	80							
1234	340	0.09	1142	80							
1236	400	0.09	1142	80							
1238	400	0.09	1142	60							

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B103**

Date: 16/06/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B103

Date: 16/06/05

Instruments

1. Video – DFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off . Also, RFC (marked DFC...) is virtually black on pc monitor, whereas it displays well on video monitor unit.
2. TDLAS CO2 failed after t/o, suspect due to overheating (v warm in the cabin this morning). Methane channel failed in flight ~1220Z.
3. Port Aft DLU – altitude went to zero and pressure to 1013mb after t/o. Reset DLU then okay.
4. Video – outboard recorder chewed up the FFC tape, replaced at 1148Z.
5. HORACE / DLU – at1208Z DRS control menu showed DRS process stopped and no flight no. Started process (option 1), entered flight no.(3) and started data recording(5). HORACE got into a loop of re-initialising DLUs so 10s worth of data followed by reset. Tried restarting DRS process (option 12), no improvement. Reset DLU CB to no avail. Stopped HORACE process (option 4 & 1) and pulled DLU CB at same time, left for a few seconds, restarted, then okay at 1225Z.

Status report

Cloud physics, NOxy, PTRms, CPI, CCN, AMS, Core Chemistry – all okay

CVI – Channel1 on PSASP saturated

WAS – Okay but preflight found small leak could not find it in time

ADA not working well

Aircraft

1. Cabin air conditioning noted in tech log.

Satcom H:- 1 call by FAAM

Flight B103 13:50:57

Heading 197 deg Speed 232 knots Height 9.9kft Press 696mb

Lat 53.3N Long 0.1W Wind 19 ms-1/ 276 deg

Temp 3.39C Dewpoint 2.22C

From 13:09:38 to now

